

ISic002750

I.Sicily inscription 002750

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Francesca Prado,system

Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2021-06-30 - Francesca Prado edited the text

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Original discovery not recorded.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 27 cm

Width 22 cm

Depth 2 cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε κ[εῖται]
2. Νώνιος Πι[---] τέκτων · κάλ[λισταόν]
4. ποτε τοῦτον [ά]νεῖ λε κίων καὶ Μοῖρα
6. ὃς κατέλειψε πατρὶ
7. λύπην δεινοτάτην
8. ἔζησε ἔτη ιβ

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1994

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645153

EDR 141112

EDCS 64901099

PHI 332879

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